

The Rise of the South: Quantifying Economic Development and Socio-Ecological Outcomes under Alternative World Orders

Abstract

This study uses the *MORDRED* model to simulate three quantitative scenarios exploring how shifts in global power distributions between the Global North and South could shape socio-economic development and environmental outcomes throughout the 21st century: *Historical legacy*, *Diverging development*, and *Reversed fortune*. The rise of the Global South, particularly the semiperiphery, drives global economic expansion and accelerates the reduction of poverty and mortality. However, socio-economic gains are accompanied by steep increases in material extraction, bioenergy demand, and a projected global warming of 3–5 °C by 2100 despite a 90%-95% greening of electricity and the expansion of bioenergy. Growth in the South drives urbanization and intensifies land-use competition, endangering ecosystems and the livelihoods of vulnerable communities. Thus, a just sustainability transition requires not only energy and resource convergence at low levels but also a fundamental reconceptualization of economic development.

Keywords

Global South; international system; Integrated assessment modeling; Socio-economic scenarios; sustainable development; climate change

1. Introduction

The Global South occupies a pivotal position in the global quest for sustainability. On the one hand, it is and will continue to be disproportionately affected by the adverse impacts of global environmental and climate change, including economic losses and forced displacement (Almulhim et al., 2024; Shan, 2023), despite its relatively small historical contribution to the global ecological crisis and the fact that per capita emissions in most Global South countries remain lower than those in the Global North (Matthews, 2016; Our World in Data, 2024). On the other hand, economic growth in the Global South has come at a considerable environmental cost, with the region now responsible for approximately 63% of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions (Fuhr, 2021). At the same time, the Global South has emerged as an innovation hub for sustainable practices and technologies and has become actively engaged in climate mitigation and adaptation efforts (Anguelovski et al., 2014; Frischmann et al., 2022; Khasru & Ambrizzi, 2023). The rise of the Global South also carries profound implications for the future of the world order, as emerging powers are already reshaping global governance, including development cooperation (Das & Janakiraman, 2026; Ghimire, 2018; Klingebiel, 2023).

Scenario development in the field of international relations (IR) can be considered a valuable tool that can be used to overcome the tendency to extrapolate the structural *status quo* into the future (Sus & Hadeed, 2020). It also provides a framework to address the political uncertainties arising from global environmental and economic transformations, in which the Global South plays an increasingly active role. Nevertheless, engagement of IR and IPE (international political economy) scholars with future studies remains limited. Only a few studies (e.g. Ansari et al., 2019; Bazilian et al., 2020) have developed energy futures that incorporate geopolitical aspects (Blondeel et al., 2024). Similarly, global climate and energy scenarios tend to overlook or underestimate the agency of Global South countries and collectives (Lauer, Carpintero, et al., 2025), despite the surge of research focusing on the Global South in the fields of sustainable development and climate change (Mazzege et al., 2025). This may partly reflect the continuing dominance of the Global North within the 'future industry' (Muiderman et al., 2023). One effort to remedy these imbalances is represented by the 'Fast Sustainability Scenario' (FST) set, particularly by '*FST4: Greener South-led development*', and '*FST5 – sufficiency economies*', in which emerging powers assume a central role in driving social, economic, environmental and geopolitical changes (Lauer, De Castro, et al., 2025).

Likewise, scenarios that explicitly explore global governance and changing power distributions mediated by politico-economic developments in both the Global South and the Global North remain underrepresented. At present, only a limited body of work focuses on future governance-related themes and power struggles, such as the future of development cooperation (Klingebiel & Sumner, 2025), future governance in the Antarctica (Frame et al., 2022), different state futures in the Global South (Cilliers & van Rooyen, 2025) and alternative global governance scenarios that focus especially on struggles within the Global South (Cruz, 2015). These scenarios often consider the environment as a direct or indirect driver interacting with economic, social, and technological developments. However, the resulting futures are predominantly qualitative and have not been systematically examined through quantitative modeling.

To address this gap, this article presents a quantitative scenario analysis that explores the socio-economic developments associated with profound shifts in the power distribution between the Global North and the Global South, as well as the implications of these shifts for global environmental dynamics. Specifically, we address three guiding questions:

1. Which macroeconomic changes could characterize a shifting power distribution between world regions?
2. What might different macroeconomic developments imply for the living standards and ways of life of populations in different world regions?
3. How could shifts in the power distribution between the Global North and South influence future changes in anthropogenic pressures on planetary systems?

Our study constitutes a first attempt to bridge the fields of IPE, global environmental and climate change research, future studies and system dynamics modeling by representing possible global socio-economic and environmental futures with a special focus on North-South relationships through an integrated assessment model (IAM).

2. Methods

In this section, we provide an overview of the model used for the scenario analysis and describe the characteristics of the quantified scenarios.

2.1. Model

The IAM selected for our scenario analysis is *MORDRED* (Model Of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development), a system dynamics model consisting of several linked sub-modules that represent different aspects of the global system. These include the world population, global economic activity, the land–energy–climate system, and the environmental impacts of economic production, such as air pollution, material extraction, and GHG emissions.

The center of *MORDRED* is constituted by a global input–output model that projects future economic developments across 25 sectors, based on scenario-dependent assumptions regarding future consumption growth rates. Technological development is represented as changes in the input coefficients of the model’s A matrix. The model also includes a simplified representation of a subsistence sector that operates outside the global economy. This sector is characterized by low productivity, zero material inputs from the world economy, and minimal environmental pollution. It sustains the poorest segments of the global population living at the margins of the global capitalist economy.

The demographic module of *MORDRED* consists of 20 age groups (0–4 years, 5–9 years, ..., 95+ years) and is used to simulate demographic developments in three world regions: the *center*, encompassing all high-income countries, the *periphery*, covering all lower-income and low-income countries, and the *semiperiphery*, including the remaining upper-middle-income countries. The model also calculates migration flows between the global economy and the subsistence sector within each region. All individuals living under subsistence conditions belong to the ‘subsistence class’, irrespective of the region. The remaining population—fully integrated into the global economy and participating in productive processes—is divided into three social classes within each region: the upper class, comprising the richest 20% of the population; the lower class, representing the poorest 30%, and the middle class with the remaining half of the population. Per capita consumption within these classes changes dynamically during simulations, influencing age-specific fertility and mortality rates.

Economic production in the world economy depends on several input factors, which vary across the 25 sectors. These include labor hours, capital, intermediate products, energy, land, and water. The model simultaneously calculates the environmental implications of economic activity

through ‘Earth intensities’ (e.g., land, water, mineral use). Impacts on the global climate system are simulated in the climate module, primarily driven by GHG emissions from fossil fuel combustion. Rising global temperatures feed back into the model through climate damage factors, which can be activated or deactivated depending on the scenario.

When required input factors are insufficient to produce the output needed to meet industrial and final demand, demand is reduced in subsequent time steps, resulting in economic contraction. However, the model can also simulate scenarios in which the scarcity of one or more input factors does not constrain economic development.

The combination of global scale and regional disaggregation of socio-demographic variables renders MORDRED particularly suitable for our study, as it allows us to track changes in both global economic–biophysical systems and sub-global development pathways. Comprehensive documentation of MORDRED, including the sectoral disaggregation, is available on GitHub (Lauer & Llases, 2025).

2.2. Scenarios

Although our scenario analysis focuses especially on development pathways in the Global South, the literature emphasizes that the Global South is not a homogeneous geopolitical, economic, social, or cultural block (Bull & Banik, 2025). There are huge disparities in economic power among Global South countries, and positions on global environmental and climate governance diverge (Mohan, 2025). However, what Global South countries have in common is a shared a common colonial heritage and/or a rather unfavorable position in the global economic order (Mazzege et al., 2025). To avoid constructing an artificial North–South dichotomy, we retain MORDRED’s division of the world into three regions—center, semiperiphery, and periphery—whose countries occupy distinct positions in the global hierarchy of economic power, reflected in differing income levels. Although the current power distribution and wealth distribution is better characterized as ‘quadrimodal’, reflected in a lower periphery, an upper periphery, the semi-periphery, and core regions (Karatasli & Kumral, 2017) for reasons of data availability and reliability we refrain from sub-dividing the periphery.

Our scenarios reflect a realist and critical traditions in IR and IPE since we focus on politico-economic power differences between regional blocs that form a hierarchical world order, despite the absence of a global monopoly of violence (cf. Beckmann & Erpul, 2024). By varying the relative positions of the center, semiperiphery, and periphery within the global politico-economic hierarchy, we derive our scenarios. In theory, six scenarios resulting from six combinations of hierarchical order are possible:

1. **Center > Semiperiphery > Periphery (CSP) – *Historical legacy***

This scenario reflects the current hierarchy, characterized by considerable consumption per capita differences between the three world regions in the initial moment of the simulation that were derived based on global consumption inequality estimates (Lahoti et al., 2016). Given that this power hierarchy has persisted since the end of the Second World War, evolving from a liberal to a neoliberal international order (Ramirez, 2025) a future in which this hierarchy is maintained throughout the 21st century cannot be ruled out. Thus, in the CSP scenario, the center maintains substantial control over the world system despite its relatively small population, enjoying disproportionately high consumption levels. Cooperation between countries occurs primarily along a North-

South axis and the center is able to implicitly shape access to resources, which can create neocolonial dynamics of control and exploitation.

2. **Semiperiphery > Center > Periphery (SCP)** – *Diverging development*

This configuration reflects ongoing trends of secular stagnation in high-income countries, strong growth in ‘emerging economies’ and low growth or decline in the world’s poorest regions (Carlos Bresser-Pereira, 2019; Fatton, 2013; Hurrell & Sengupta, 2012). In this global future, the divide widens between Global South countries that achieve industrialization and those that remain marginalized. International cooperation increasingly takes on a South–South character, as the semiperiphery seeks both to promote development in the periphery and to secure privileged access to its resources (Bull & Banik, 2025; Ghimire, 2018). Meanwhile, the center strives to avoid further losses of global influence.

3. **Semiperiphery > Periphery > Center (SPC)** – *Reversed fortune*

In this scenario, both the semiperiphery and periphery succeed in leveraging the global economic system to their advantage, while the center fails to revive growth and gradually becomes trapped in an unfavorable position as capital flows start to shift away from the center. In this scenario, ‘development cooperation’ would acquire a South-to-North character as the current center becomes the future periphery. Although this scenario appears less likely at present, it remains plausible and yields dynamics that are rarely explored in the literature.

The remaining possible combinations (C>P>S, P>C>S, P>S>C) are deemed highly improbable and are therefore excluded from analysis.

We are interested in ‘business as usual’ scenarios lacking fundamental changes towards sustainability, given that those changes have not occurred during the last 50 years despite dire warnings and heated debates about the transgression of biophysical limits (Meadows et al., 1972). Therefore, all scenarios assume continuous economic growth along industrialization- and extraction-based development pathways. However, it is also assumed that the most powerful geopolitical actors invest in developing green technologies and implementing green structural changes. Given that the semiperiphery and periphery together represent the vast majority of the world’s population, their growing economic and political weight is expected to drive large-scale environmental policy implementation. Thus, SPC and SCP are associated with more extensive green structural transformation than CSP.

Importantly, in this scenario analysis we focus exclusively on the impacts of economic activity on planetary biophysical systems, rather than the reverse effects of altered planetary systems on the global economy—a feedback recognized as crucial for future international politico-economic developments (Katz-Rosene, 2019). This simplification reduces analytical complexity while clarifying the environmental implications of economic growth in the absence of strict biophysical limits. Accordingly, we deactivate the land scarcity feedback in the model and adopt very optimistic assumptions regarding the availability of fossil resources (BGR, 2020) in all scenarios.

Simulations project model variables to the end of the 21st century based on MORDRED version 1.1.1, which features exogenously defined consumption inequality pathways and includes an urbanization indicator. Table 1 provides an overview of the main qualitative and quantitative assumptions for the three scenarios.

Driver	CSP	SCP	SPC
International cooperation paradigm	North-South cooperation.	South-South cooperation.	South-South & South-North cooperation.
Economic development paradigm	Industrial, growth-based, extractivism, high dependency on wage labor.		
	$\Delta \frac{K}{x} = 0$ (constant sectoral capital intensities)	$\Delta_{2100-2019} \frac{K}{x} = 1.2$	$\Delta_{2100-2019} \frac{K}{x} = 1.3$
	Constant material and mineral intensities of the economy (constant input coefficients for the material extraction sector (sector 4)). $\Delta a_{4,1} = \Delta a_{4,2} = \Delta a_{4,3} = \dots = \Delta a_{4,25} = 0$		
	<i>annual working hours = 2080</i> <i>maximum participation rate = 0.9</i>		
Industrial development	Weak in P, strong in S, medium in C.	Strong in S, almost stagnant in C, Weak in P.	Strong in P & S, deindustrialization in C.
	$g_{C,U20} = 1.48\%$ $g_{C,M50} = 1.24\%$ $g_{C,L30} = 1.23\%$ $g_{S,U20} = 2.20\%$ $g_{S,M50} = 2.71\%$ $g_{S,L30} = 2.70\%$ $g_{S,U20} = 0.85\%$ $g_{S,M50} = 1.24\%$ $g_{S,L30} = 1.52\%$	$g_{C,U20} = 1.39\%$ $g_{C,M50} = 1.30\%$ $g_{C,L30} = 1.02\%$ $g_{S,U20} = 3.15\%$ $g_{S,M50} = 3.66\%$ $g_{S,L30} = 3.65\%$ $g_{S,U20} = 2.16\%$ $g_{S,M50} = 2.16\%$ $g_{S,L30} = 2.16\%$	$g_{C,U20} = -0.19\%$ $g_{C,M50} = 0.06\%$ $g_{C,L30} = 0.19\%$ $g_{S,U20} = 4.07\%$ $g_{S,M50} = 4.58\%$ $g_{S,L30} = 4.86\%$ $g_{S,U20} = 2.88\%$ $g_{S,M50} = 3.13\%$ $g_{S,L30} = 3.04\%$
International inequality	Moderate decrease (low convergence).	Decreasing (strong convergence).	Decreasing (medium convergence).
	$g_{C,\emptyset} = 1.29\%$ $g_{S,\emptyset} = 2.60\%$	$g_{C,\emptyset} = 1.23\%$ $g_{S,\emptyset} = 3.55\%$	$g_{C,\emptyset} = 0.05\%$ $g_{S,\emptyset} = 4.56\%$

	$g_{P,\emptyset} = 1.25\%$	$g_{P,\emptyset} = 2.16\%$	$g_{P,\emptyset} = 3.05\%$
Internal inequality	C: slightly increasing S: slightly decreasing P: decreasing.	C: increasing S: slightly decreasing P: constant.	C: decreasing S: decreasing P: slightly decreasing.
	$g_{C,U20} - g_{C,M50} = 0.24$ $g_{C,L30} - g_{C,M50} = -0.01$ $g_{S,U20} - g_{S,M50} = -0.51$ $g_{S,L30} - g_{S,M50} = -0.01$ $g_{S,U20} - g_{S,M50} = -0.39$ $g_{S,L30} - g_{S,M50} = 0.28$	$g_{C,U20} - g_{C,M50} = 0.09$ $g_{C,L30} - g_{C,M50} = -0.28$ $g_{S,U20} - g_{S,M50} = -0.51$ $g_{S,L30} - g_{S,M50} = -0.01$ $g_{S,U20} - g_{S,M50} = 0$ $g_{S,L30} - g_{S,M50} = 0$	$g_{C,U20} - g_{C,M50} = -0.25$ $g_{C,L30} - g_{C,M50} = 0.13$ $g_{S,U20} - g_{S,M50} = -0.51$ $g_{S,L30} - g_{S,M50} = 0.28$ $g_{S,U20} - g_{S,M50} = -0.25$ $g_{S,L30} - g_{S,M50} = -0.09$
Control of resource access (result of industrial development and inequality)	C>S>P	S>C>P	S>P>C
Energy transition, technological development and changes in final demand	Improvement of industrial processes: 10%. Medium greening of electricity mix: reduction of fossil electricity inputs by 90%. Low electrification: Reduction of non-electric energy inputs by 20%. Moderate greening of non-electric energy: substitution of 20% of fossil energy inputs with bioenergy (all changes refer to 2100 compared to 2019 and to both industry and final demand).	Improvement of industrial processes: 10%. Medium greening of electricity mix: reduction of fossil electricity inputs by 90%. Moderate electrification: Reduction of non-electric energy inputs by 25%. Medium greening of non-electric energy: substitution of 25% of fossil energy inputs with bioenergy.	Improvement of industrial processes: 10%. High greening of electricity mix: reduction of fossil electricity inputs by 95%. Medium electrification: Reduction of non-electric energy inputs by 30%. High greening of non-electric energy: substitution of 30% of fossil energy inputs with bioenergy.
Sectoral labor productivity development	Medium: Global sectoral labor productivities by 2100 approach labor productivity levels of the center in 2019.	High: 20% higher labor productivities than in CSP.	High: 50% higher labor productivities than in CSP.

Land productivity & land scarcity	Land scarcity feedback not activated, i.e. no limits to growth due to potential land shortages. High implicit land productivity increases.	
Control of land in rural areas	Prioritization of land demands from world economy.	Equal priority of land demands from world economy and subsistence sector.
	Land types required by global economy > land required by subsistence sector, primary forest > other ecosystems.	Land types required by global economy & subsistence sector > primary forest > other ecosystems.
Forest protection policy	Medium.	
	22200000 km ² of forests protected (50% primary forest, 50% secondary forest).	
Fossil resource availability & accessibility	High.	
	Ultimately recoverable fossil resources: 495390 EJ. Favorable extraction cost estimation.	
Climate sensitivity	Simulations with low, medium and high sensitivity of the climate system to anthropogenic perturbations.	
Adverse environmental impacts	No climate damages activated.	
Migration dynamics between subsistence and world economy	Moderate willingness to migrate from subsistence to world economy; low willingness to migrate from world economy to subsistence. Willingness to integrate into world economy increases linearly with the difference in the per capita consumption between the poorest class integrated into the world economy and the monetized consumption of the subsistence class within a world region, reaching 100% when the consumption inside the world economy is 5 times the subsistence consumption. Willingness to migrate to the subsistence economy decreases linearly with the difference in the per capita consumption between the poorest class integrated into the world economy and the consumption of the subsistence class within a world region.	

Table 1: Main qualitative and quantitative scenario assumptions.

3. Results

This section presents the key quantitative outcomes for the CSP, SCP, and SPC scenarios. Results are organized into three thematic areas: macroeconomic changes, socio-demographic developments, and environmental impacts.

3.1. Macroeconomic changes in the world system

In all scenarios, global economic output—including the production of intermediate and final goods—rises continuously throughout the simulation. As shown in Figure 1a, different power constellations in the international system are linked to distinct levels of overall economic growth. While global output triples during the 80-year simulation in CSP – Historical legacy, it increases nearly sixfold in SCP – Diverging development, and sevenfold in SPC – Reversed fortune. These results indicate that shifts away from the current power hierarchy stimulate global economic expansion and accelerate the development of productive capacities.

Interestingly, in the SPC scenario, desired consumption growth rates are so high that during the final two decades total demand can no longer be met with the available labor supply, even though both sectoral labor productivity and the global workforce grow faster than in the other scenarios. This leads to a slowdown in economic growth toward the end of the 21st century, illustrating that, even in the absence of strong biophysical limits to growth, economic development can still be constrained by labor availability.

Differences in total output growth between the scenarios are mirrored by variations in public (government) and private (household) consumption at the global level. However, at the regional level, these variables do not necessarily follow global trends (Figure 1b,c). Public consumption in the center grows by approximately 84% in both the CSP and SCP scenarios but declines by 56% in SPC. By the end of the century, government consumption in the semiperiphery exceeds that of other world regions in all scenarios. In CSP, public consumption in the semiperiphery is 1.6 times that of the center and 4.8 times that of the periphery by 2100; in SCP, the ratios are 3.6 and 4.4; and in SPC, 22 and 4.9 times higher, respectively.

In the periphery, public consumption quadruples between 2020 and 2100 in CSP and increases 11.5-fold in SPC. However, even with these high growth rates, government consumption in the periphery at the end of the century is only 9.5% higher than that of the center in CSP. This makes SPC the scenario with the greatest divergence in public consumption, particularly during the second half of the simulation. In 2060, public consumption in the center falls to 6.5 trillion €, slightly below that of the periphery (7 trillion €), while the semiperiphery rises to 23 trillion €. By 2100, the center's spending drops by another 3.1 trillion €, whereas the periphery more than doubles to 15.6 trillion €, and the semiperiphery more than triples to 76.2 trillion €, compared to their 2060 levels.

A similar pattern is observed for private consumption. In SPC, private consumption in 2100 reaches 217 trillion € in the semiperiphery, 74 trillion € in the periphery, and 11.6 trillion € in the center. Although the center's total household consumption decreases by 57% compared to the start of the simulation, it remains comparable to the semiperiphery's total in 2020 and nearly doubles that of the periphery at the beginning of the simulation, despite its smaller

population size. Consumption patterns in the other scenarios show consistent growth across all regions, though faster in the semiperiphery and periphery under SCP than under CSP.

An analysis of public and private consumption at the regional level reveals that the slowdown in global output in SPC is primarily driven by reduced consumption growth in the periphery, while the semiperiphery continues to expand despite global labor shortages. Differences in workforce evolution are minor for the center and semiperiphery, both of which experience a continuous decline from 2035 onward in all scenarios. In contrast, the periphery’s workforce peaks latest in CSP and earliest in SPC. By the end of the century, the working population in the periphery ranges from 3.21 billion (CSP) to 2.89 billion (SPC), with SCP falling in between (3.05 billion) (Figure 1d).

The size of the potential workforce—defined as the population integrated into the global economy and aged 15–64—serves as an indicator of a region’s economic and political power, as it represents both a source of capital accumulation and of potential military recruitment. Thus, the relatively large workforce in CSP somewhat contradicts the periphery’s weak global position. However, in this scenario, the periphery lacks the organizational capacity to strategically deploy its labor force, which instead functions as cheap labor stabilizing the global regime of production.

The combination of declining government and household consumption and a shrinking workforce renders the former center economically insignificant in SPC. Since it neither offers a big market nor a large and cheap working force or significant exploitable resources, this implies a strong need for the center to specialize in high-skill industries producing rare, high-value goods. Nonetheless, even in the CSP and SCP scenarios, the Global North is expected to lose relative power when considering the aggregated economic potential of the Global South.

Figure 1: a) Annual world output, b) public spending, c) total household consumption and d) potential working force per world region in the CSP (blue), SCP (orange) and SPC (green) scenario.

3.2. Development indicators

Rising living standards among the poorest 30% of the semiperiphery and periphery in SCP and SPC lead to a continuous decline in the number of people dependent on the subsistence economy (Figure 2b). By 2050, over 90% of the subsistence population has transitioned into the global economy, and by 2060, the subsistence sector has virtually disappeared in all scenarios. The urbanization indicator rises from below 0.5 to 0.8, suggesting a highly urbanized Global South characterized by diminished alternative livelihoods and a nearly complete integration of workers into the global accumulation regime.

In the CSP scenario, limited protection for land used by the subsistence class leads to the integration of subsistence land into the global economy as industrial demand for land increases. Populations previously reliant on these territories are forced to join the global labor force, pointing to processes of expropriation, capitalization, and industrialization of land driven by capitalist expansion.

Economic growth also increases public expenditure on education and health, although developments differ by region and scenario. In the center, per capita public spending on these sectors more than doubles in CSP and SCP but stagnates in SPC, declining in the final two decades. In the semiperiphery, declining population combined with strong economic growth produces an increase in per capita spending across all scenarios, most notably in SPC, where it reaches far higher levels than the other regions (Figure 2a). In the periphery, per capita spending rises modestly in CSP—by 78 € between 2020 and 2060, and by 124 € between 2060 and 2100. In contrast, spending increases by 646 € in SCP and 940 € in SPC. While per capita expenditure in the semiperiphery reaches and surpasses the center's initial level between 2055 (SPC) and 2085 (CSP), the periphery does not attain the center's initial values in any scenario.

High growth rates combined with declining inequality in the semiperiphery drive exponential increases in per capita consumption among the poorest 30%. In 2060, annual per capita consumption in this class ranges from 3,800 € to 9,000 €, and by 2100, from 11,000 € to nearly 43,000 €. In contrast, consumption among the poorest 30% of the periphery ranges from 3,000 € to 7,350 € in 2100 (Figure 2c). The relatively high consumption of poorer classes in SPC contributes to the labor scarcity observed in that scenario: once lower-class consumption rises sufficiently, there are no longer large low-consuming labor groups available to sustain unequal global labor exchanges, limiting the model's ability to meet total demand.

Across all scenarios, public spending, rising consumption of the poorest classes, and declining subsistence populations lead to the global eradication of extreme poverty within the first half of the simulation. Although per capita consumption in the center declines in SPC, this does not translate into an increase in extreme poverty.

Nevertheless, regional disparities in consumption and living standards persist throughout the century, resulting in differences in life expectancy. Child mortality in the center remains low in all scenarios. In the semiperiphery, child mortality declines rapidly in the early decades, reaching the center's level by around 2065 in SPC, 2075 in SCP, and 2100 in CSP (Figure 2d). The periphery shows the highest initial child mortality, and although absolute reductions are greatest in this world region, convergence with the center's levels is achieved only in SPC. In SCP and CSP,

the periphery's child mortality index remains 13% and 94% higher than that of the center by 2100.

Unlike child mortality, the adult mortality rate in the center differs between the scenarios and increases during the last decades of the SPC simulation while it continues to fall in the CSP and SCP scenarios (Figure 2e). By 2100, adult mortality in the center is still lower than in the periphery but higher than in the semiperiphery, signaling a relative decline in living standards that would be even more pronounced for the middle and lower classes if there was no reduction in internal inequality in this scenario. In the semiperiphery and periphery, adult mortality declines continuously, with faster improvements in SCP and SPC than in CSP. In CSP, the adult mortality index in the periphery is still 1.9 times that of the semiperiphery and 3.9 times that of the center in 2060; by 2100 it remains 3.2 times that of the center and twice the level observed in SPC. In the semiperiphery, adult mortality approaches the level of the center by the end of the 21st century in SCP but convergence is incomplete in CSP.

Due to demographic changes, the average age of the population dependent on the global economy increases in all regions throughout the 21st century. However, population aging occurs more slowly in the semiperiphery and periphery under CSP and SCP because of higher birth rates associated with lower consumption levels (Figure 2f).

Overall, the results indicate that changes in the global power distribution away from the status quo benefit socio-economic development in the Global South, reflected in an earlier elimination of extreme poverty, higher living standards and lower child and adult mortality.

Figure 2: a) Public per capita expenses in the health and education sector in every world region, b) people depending on subsistence economies, c) consumption of the lower classes in the semiperiphery and periphery, d) child mortality index per world region (calculated with the initial child mortality rate of the semiperiphery), e) mortality index for adults per world region, based on mortality rates of adults aged 35-39, f) average age in the world economy at the regional level in the CSP (blue), SCP (orange) and SPC (green) scenario.

3.3. Environmental indicators

Environmental impacts can be classified into material extraction (Figure 3) and climate-related impacts (Figure 4).

Since all scenarios maintain an extractivist development paradigm, the production of biomass, bulk materials, and precious metals increases regardless of future power configurations (Figure 3a-c). Nevertheless, the socio-economic and political rise to power of the Global South is clearly linked to significantly higher levels of extractive activity. Global industrial roundwood production more than triples in CSP and increases fivefold in SCP. The emerging labor scarcity in SPC leads to lower increases in material extraction towards the end of the 21st century but roundwood production nevertheless increases 6-fold in the SPC scenario. Given that industrial wood extraction is linked to deforestation and biodiversity loss (Fuller et al., 2019; Goodman et al., 2024), these results suggest intensifying pressures on forest ecosystems during the 21st century.

The same pattern is observed for bulk materials such as aluminum and salt, as well as for precious metals like gold and silver. Most of the increase in extraction occurs in the second half of the simulation: between 2060 and 2100, annual aluminum and salt production rises by 83 Mt and 370 Mt in CSP, 268 Mt and 1,187 Mt in SCP, and 357 Mt and 1,551 Mt in SPC. In the same period, gold and silver production increases by 70% and 98 % in CSP, by 160% and 225% in SCP, and by 172% and 254 % in SPC, respectively.

The production levels of bulk materials reached mid-century and beyond make current extraction levels appear marginal (Figure 3b). Given the multiple types of water and air pollution linked to aluminum and salt production that can affect ecosystems as well as human health (Brough & Jouhara, 2020; Ekrami et al., 2021; Ocholla et al., 2013) the simulation outcomes point to an increased risk of ecosystem degradation and environmental distribution conflicts in the future.

Cumulatively, over the 80-years simulation more than 24% (CSP), 37% (SCP) and 48% (SPC) of the ultimately available gold resources and more than 22% (CSP), 37% (SCP) and 49% (SPC) of the ultimately available silver resources, as estimated by Henckens (2021), are extracted. For copper, between 30% and 63% of ultimately available resources are consumed. Although the simulations do not account for historical extraction or rising costs as ore grades decline, even with high technological progress, meeting mineral demand beyond the 21st century appears uncertain. This underscores the importance of recycling and material-efficiency policies, especially under scenarios where the Global South gains power and economic weight.

Another important type of material extraction comes from the fossil fuels sector given the material use of fossil resources. While coal plays a relatively minor role as industrial feedstock, the material use of natural gas and especially of oil increases strongly (Figure 3d). Thus, the non-material use of fossil resources creates a continued dependency on the fossil sector even in scenarios with a higher decarbonization rate than the scenarios simulated here.

Figure 3: a) Global industrial roundwood production, b) global production of aluminum and salt, c) global production of gold and silver, d) global non-energy use of fossil resources in the CSP (blue), SCP (orange) and SPC (green) scenario.

By aggregating fossil resource extraction for energetic and material use we derive the projected changes in total fossil resource extraction during the scenarios (Figure 4a). While the extraction of oil and natural gas increases in all scenarios, coal extraction declines in the CSP scenario and stabilizes in the second half of the SPC scenario. As oil demand remains strong but reserves are more limited than for coal (BGR, 2020), future technological innovation will be crucial to prevent growth constraints from oil depletion.

Moderate environmental policies in all scenarios lead to a gradual replacement of fossil energy by electricity and biomass-based energy (Figure 4a). Although renewable energy use increases most in SPC and least in CSP, the latter produces the lowest GHG emissions overall. Assuming constant non-combustion emission intensities, annual emissions rise from 50 Gt CO₂-equivalents to 79 Gt in CSP, 142 Gt in SCP, and 163 Gt in SPC. If non-combustion-related emission intensities decrease by 40% by 2100, end-of-century emissions are 16 Gt (CSP), 15 Gt (SCP), and 36 Gt (SPC) lower—highlighting the importance of mitigating industrial emissions from CH₄, N₂O, SF₆, HFCs and PFCs.

The larger population size of the semiperiphery and the periphery is the main driver of total consumption demand in SCP and SPC. The resulting increase in the scale of economic activity results in greater demand for fossil energy resources that are not offset by the higher rate of decarbonization in those scenarios, compared to CSP. In the latter, the feedback effect between lower consumption levels and higher birth rates leads to a slower decline in the population size of the periphery and results in a somewhat higher emission pathway.

Simulated emissions correspond to an increase in global mean temperature of 3.06°C - 5.15°C by 2100 relative to the pre-industrial period, depending on assumptions regarding non-combustion GHG intensity improvements and natural climate feedbacks.

Thus, under a conventional development paradigm with moderate environmental ambition, higher living standards for the Global South are accompanied by substantially greater anthropogenic pressure on the global environment. The resulting destabilization of planetary systems (IPCC, 2021, 2022; Richardson et al., 2023) risks amplifying geopolitical tensions in the global system stemming from the Global South's rise to power in the SCP and the SPC scenario (Hurrell & Sengupta, 2012; Moore, 2024).

Figure 4: Changes in model variables in the CSP (blue), SCP (orange) and SPC (green) scenario. a) Global extraction of oil, natural gas and coal (given in EJ of primary energy), b) global electricity and biomass-based energy, c) world annual GHG emissions and d) global average temperature change with respect to 1850. Dots describe changes in simulations with falling GHG intensities for non-combustion-related emissions and without climate feedbacks; lines describes changes in simulations with constant GHG intensities for non-combustion-related emissions and without climate feedbacks; dashed lines describe changes in simulations with constant GHG intensities and with feedbacks within the climate systems.

4. Discussion

Our simulations explore quantitative dynamics that might accompany or signal profound changes in world orders and international power distribution due to the rise of the Global South, and, thus, constitute an attempt to complement qualitative scenario analyses in the field of IR and IPE with the additional insights that can be gained by employing modeling tools.

Nevertheless, our results must be interpreted in the context of the specific scenario assumptions made and must consider the structural features of the model used. Hence, we want to stress that the projected socio-economic and biophysical changes result from the assumption of material-intensive development, combined with the implementation of concrete green technologies that can be represented through the model's input-output structure. Our scenario analysis excludes green technologies that are not (yet) scalable or come with strong socio-ecological risks, such as carbon capture and storage (CCS), bioenergy with carbon capture and storage (BECCS), large-scale geoengineering or nuclear fusion (Braun et al., 2025; Gi et al., 2020; Günther & Ekardt, 2022; Parson & Reynolds, 2021; Sekera & Lichtenberger, 2020; Surprise, 2020). Likewise, the MORDRED model is not capable of representing new patterns of cooperation and competition that can be expected under scenarios of changing world orders. Especially, intensifying geopolitical tensions will impact future technological development, the transformation of global energy systems and climate politics. While some scholars anticipate a deceleration of mitigation efforts driven by diminished international cooperation, altered trade dynamics, diversion of financial resources, military-related emissions, and asset destruction (Block et al., 2025) others acknowledge a multitude of risks but also contend that competitive pressures may stimulate

technological innovation and increased investment in renewable energy to enhance national energy security (Blondeel et al., 2024; Moore, 2024).

Nevertheless, we hold that, overall, the growing tensions in the international system associated with a potential rise of the emerging powers among the Global South, will act as an obstacle to achieving levels of climate mitigation significantly higher than what has been simulated in the present study, especially because of the growth-enhancing effect of competition. As the scenario results show, the scale effect dominates over the effects of changes in technology and in the economy's sectoral composition, and, thus, more growth will imply a higher level of global warming.

Importantly, scenario trajectories are not only sensitive to dynamics that are presently not represented in MORDRED, such as migration, interregional trade, social conflicts and wars, but also to biophysical feedbacks that have been deactivated for the present analysis (see methods section). One consequence of this modeling decision is a relative neglect of the simulations for future land-related developments and risks. For example, if fast and continuous land productivity improvements in the Global South can no longer be maintained due to adverse effects of environmental degradation and climate change, the availability of land will become a key limiting factor to global economic development, slowing down the rise of the Global South.

In all three scenarios, rising material extraction and increasing demand for bioenergy imply strong pressures on territories in the Global South, potentially endangering the livelihoods of vulnerable socio-economic groups such as Indigenous and peasant communities (Owen, Kemp, Harris, et al., 2022; Owen, Kemp, Lechner, et al., 2022; Temper et al., 2020). The conservation and restoration of the Global South's remaining biodiversity-rich ecosystems, which perform key roles for planetary life-support systems, are clearly at odds with the strong economic expansion in all scenarios, especially in the SCP and SPC scenarios, given that large-scale agricultural land acquisitions tend to contribute to biodiversity loss and often fall within biodiversity hotspots (Davis et al., 2023). The commodification of biodiversity conservation and associated violence against marginalized population groups can thus be expected to increase in all three simulated futures (cf. Sène, 2024). Paradoxically, biodiversity conservation and mining activities increasingly overlap and are linked to land grabbing as local communities lose control over land and resources (Vuola, 2022). This is mirrored in 'renewables grabbing' (Scheidel et al., 2023) spurred by the global energy transition.

Apart from the negative effects for local communities in the Global South, the combined pressure of climate change impacts and climate change mitigation, food production and energy generation on land also generates risks for planetary environmental and international political stability (King et al., 2023) not captured in our scenario simulations. Ironically, pressure on Global South territories will be higher in scenarios with a strong economic development in the Global South than in those futures that are characterized by a continuation of Global North dominance. At the same time, a rise in the global power hierarchy will enable the South to control strategic landmasses and resource extraction situated in its own territory (cf. Mohapatra, 2017).

Additionally, as emerging countries of the semiperiphery acquire 'imperial' powers in the SCP and the SPC scenario they might increasingly exert indirect territorial control over the periphery and even the center (cf. Das & Janakiraman, 2026). This could result in new dynamics of land acquisitions and investment flows with a reduced protagonism from transnational companies based in the Global North.

Given the projected demographic and economic developments in our scenario exercise, we argue that the Global South—particularly the semiperiphery—will emerge as the key political actor of the 21st century, serving not only as a major driver of climate change but also as the region most exposed to the adverse effects of local and global environmental change. Currently, the global polycrisis affects and constrains internal development in the Global South, which might render our scenarios too optimistic (Adam & Rena, 2024). However, if the Global South succeeds in expanding its economic and political influence, it will become the main protagonist in addressing, alleviating and resolving this unfolding polycrisis, with the world's long-term sustainability critically depending on its readiness to assume its new responsibilities in shaping the norms of global governance.

The land-related risks linked to our simulation scenarios not only point to the importance of including justice considerations in land-use scenarios to conserve biodiversity while preventing land-grabbing (Venier-Cambron et al., 2024) but also indicate the need to contemplate alternative development pathways for the Global South and North alike. The environmental assessment of the scenarios has shown that approximating living standards of the periphery to the levels characterizing the Global North at present under a conventional growth-based development pathway would have devastating effects on land and material extraction, and would produce emission pathways linked to very high levels of global warming, resulting in potentially catastrophic climate change effects. Additionally, the CSP and SCP scenarios reflect the possibility of growing accumulation of wealth in some parts of the global South alongside persistent poverty and structural exclusion in many other parts, reflecting a capitalist accumulation model incapable of delivering high levels of well-being to its population in a rapid, equitable and environmentally sustainable way (Nilsen, 2025). A just and sustainable transition therefore requires not only energy convergence between the Global North and South at relatively low levels (Hickel & Slamersak, 2022) but also a fundamental reconceptualization of 'development' in the Global South that transcends the paradigm of capitalist industrial growth (Gerber & Raina, 2018).

Today's emerging powers have become a key force in sustaining and globalizing capitalist accumulation logics (Hurrell & Sengupta, 2012), which appears to contradict the Global South's aspiration for systemic transformation and global justice (Bull & Banik, 2025). Nevertheless, practices, experiences, and theories from the Global South—though frequently overlooked—hold significant potential to inform social imaginaries that challenge capitalism as the dominant order (Diniz et al., 2020; Hollender, 2018; Jimenez et al., 2022; Zondi, 2016) and could act as important sources for future global environmental and economic scenario studies that are interested in radically changed global structures and world orders.

5. Conclusion

In this article we have conducted a quantitative scenario analysis to explore conceivable socio-economic and environmental consequences of different development pathways in the Global South and the associated changes in the global power distribution between the Global North and Global South. We found that shifts in the international power distribution towards the Global South is linked to stronger economic growth, a faster stabilization and decline of the size of the world population and global labor force, and higher public and private consumption in the South. In general, changes in world order away from the status quo foster socio-economic development

in the Global South, reflected in an earlier elimination of extreme poverty, higher living standards and mortality rates across all age groups. However, the rise of the Global South is also linked to an even faster increase in anthropogenic pressure on the Earth system, with strong growth in material extraction and land demands, as well as projected levels of global warming ranging from 3 to over 5 °C by 2100, compared to the pre-industrial reference period. Thus, although none of the development pathways of the Global South is sustainable in the long term, scenarios with strong growth in the semiperiphery and periphery further increase environmental and geopolitical risks. Consequently, it is important to explore post-capitalist and post-growth development pathways in both the Global North and South that can achieve the basic human need of the world population without destabilizing the biophysical Earth system. As the Global South unites a large and relatively young population, higher growth rates as well as higher levels of inequality and extreme poverty, emerging states from the Global South will likely become the main protagonist in the global quest for sustainability and have the potential to act as key drivers for a post-capitalist development paradigm in a radically changed global governance system and world order..

References

- Adam, H., & Rena, R. (2024). *Polycrisis and economic development in the global South*. Routledge.
- Almulhim, A. I., Alverio, G. N., Sharifi, A., Shaw, R., Huq, S., Mahmud, M. J., Ahmad, S., & Abubakar, I. R. (2024). Climate-induced migration in the Global South: An in depth analysis. *Npj Climate Action*, 3(1), 47. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44168-024-00133-1>
- Anguelovski, I., Chu, E., & Carmin, J. (2014). Variations in approaches to urban climate adaptation: Experiences and experimentation from the global South. *Global Environmental Change*, 27, 156–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2014.05.010>
- Ansari, D., Holz, F., & Al-Kuhlani, H. (2019). *Energy, climate, and policy towards 2055: An interdisciplinary energy outlook (DIW-REM Outlook)* (Issue 139). DIW Berlin: Politikberatung kompakt.
- Bazilian, M., Bradshaw, M., Gabriel, J., Goldthau, A., & Westphal, K. (2020). Four scenarios of the energy transition: Drivers, consequences, and implications for geopolitics. *WIREs Climate Change*, 11(2), e625. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.625>
- Beckmann, N. A., & Erpul, O. (2024). Realism's Timeless Wisdom and its Relevance for the Global South. *All Azimuth: A Journal of Foreign Policy and Peace*, 13(1), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.20991/allazimuth.1413433>
- BGR. (2020). *BGR Energy Study 2019 – Data and Developments Concerning German and Global energy supplies*. Hannover. https://www.bgr.bund.de/EN/Themen/Energie/Downloads/energiestudie_2019_en.pdf;jsessionid=ADF18B2529B3E89FC705FDF390A57BA4.internet002?_blob=publicationFile&v=6
- Block, K., Li, M., Gärtner, J., & Lenzen, M. (2025). Geopolitical conflict impedes climate change mitigation. *Npj Climate Action*, 4(1), 33. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44168-025-00224-7>
- Blondeel, M., Price, J., Bradshaw, M., Pye, S., Dodds, P., Kuzemko, C., & Bridge, G. (2024). Global energy scenarios: A geopolitical reality check. *Global Environmental Change*, 84, 102781.
- Braun, J., Werner, C., Gerten, D., Stenzel, F., Schaphoff, S., & Lucht, W. (2025). Multiple planetary boundaries preclude biomass crops for carbon capture and storage outside of agricultural areas. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 6(1), 102.
- Brough, D., & Jouhara, H. (2020). The aluminium industry: A review on state-of-the-art technologies, environmental impacts and possibilities for waste heat recovery. *International Journal of Thermofluids*, 1, 100007.
- Bull, B., & Banik, D. (2025). The Rebirth of the Global South: Geopolitics, Imageries and Developmental Realities. *Forum for Development Studies*, 52(2), 195–214. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08039410.2025.2490696>
- Carlos Bresser-Pereira, L. (2019). Secular Stagnation, Low Growth, and Financial Instability. *International Journal of Political Economy*, 48(1), 21–40. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08911916.2018.1550949>
- Cilliers, J., & van Rooyen, M. (2025). *State Futures in the Global South*. African futures and innovation programme. <https://futures.issafrica.org/thematic/20-futures-of-the-state-in-the-global-south>
- Cruz, S. O. (2015). Alternative futures of global governance: Scenarios and perspectives from the Global South. *Foresight*.
- Das, S., & Janakiraman, K. R. (2026). Empire and International Order: Decolonial Perspective. In *Decolonising International Relations* (pp. 152–167). Routledge.
- Davis, K. F., Müller, M. F., Rulli, M. C., Tatlhego, M., Ali, S., Baggio, J. A., Dell'Angelo, J., Jung, S., Kehoe, L., Niles, M. T., & Eckert, S. (2023). Transnational agricultural land acquisitions threaten

- biodiversity in the Global South. *Environmental Research Letters*, 18(2), 024014.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/acb2de>
- Diniz, S. C., Fernandes, B. S., & De Melo Monte-Mór, R. L. (2020). Social solidarity economy in a decolonial sense? Approaches from the Brazilian case. *Soziale Passagen*, 12(2), 313–329.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12592-020-00362-1>
- Ekrami, J., Nemati Mansour, S., Mosaferi, M., & Yamini, Y. (2021). Environmental impact assessment of salt harvesting from the salt lakes. *Journal of Environmental Health Science and Engineering*, 19(1), 365–377.
- Fatton, R. (2013). *Haiti: Trapped in the outer periphery*. Lynne Rienner Publishers.
- Frame, B., Yermakova, Y., Flamm, P., Nicklin, G., De Paula, G., Badhe, R., & Tuñez, F. (2022). Antarctica's Gateways and Gatekeepers: Polar scenarios in a polarising Anthropocene. *The Anthropocene Review*, 9(3), 392–402.
- Frischmann, C. J., Mehra, M., Alvarez, J., Jankowska, E., Jones, H., Namasivayam, A., & Yussuff, A. (2022). The Global South is the climate movement's unsung leader. *Nature Climate Change*, 12(5), 410–412. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01351-3>
- Fuhr, H. (2021). The rise of the Global South and the rise in carbon emissions. *Third World Quarterly*, 42(11), 2724–2746.
- Fuller, T. L., Narins, T. P., Nackoney, J., Bonebrake, T. C., Sesink Clee, P., Morgan, K., Tróchez, A., Bocuma Meñe, D., Bongwele, E., Njabo, K. Y., Anthony, N. M., Gonder, M. K., Kahn, M., Allen, W. R., & Smith, T. B. (2019). Assessing the impact of China's timber industry on Congo Basin land use change. *Area*, 51(2), 340–349. <https://doi.org/10.1111/area.12469>
- Gerber, J.-F., & Raina, R. S. (2018). Post-growth in the global south? Some reflections from India and Bhutan. *Ecological Economics*, 150, 353–358.
- Ghimire, S. (2018). Rising powers and security: A false dawn of the pro-south world order? *Global Change, Peace & Security*, 30(1), 37–55.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14781158.2018.1431878>
- Gi, K., Sano, F., Akimoto, K., Hiwatari, R., & Tobita, K. (2020). Potential contribution of fusion power generation to low-carbon development under the Paris Agreement and associated uncertainties. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 27, 100432.
- Goodman, R. C., Van Hensbergen, H. J., Bengtsson, K., Kaplan, A., & Persson, M. (2024). Transforming the tropical timber industry could be the key to realizing the potential of forests and forest products. *One Earth*, 7(7), 1142–1146.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2024.06.016>
- Günther, P., & Ekardt, F. (2022). Human Rights and Large-Scale Carbon Dioxide Removal: Potential Limits to BECCS and DACCS Deployment. *Land*, 11(12), 2153.
- Henckens, T. (2021). Scarce mineral resources: Extraction, consumption and limits of sustainability. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 169, 105511.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2021.105511>
- Hickel, J., & Slamersak, A. (2022). Existing climate mitigation scenarios perpetuate colonial inequalities. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 6(7), e628–e631.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(22\)00092-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(22)00092-4)
- Hollender, R. (2018). Anti, Alternative, and Post: A Review of Post-Growth A Review of Post-Growth Approaches to Radical Transformation in the Global South. *American Review of Political Economy*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.38024/arpe.147>
- Hurrell, A., & Sengupta, S. (2012). Emerging powers, North–South relations and global climate politics. *International Affairs*, 88(3), 463–484.

- IPCC. (2021). *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA,.
- IPCC. (2022). *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability. Contribution of Working Group II to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. Cambridge University Press. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK and New York, NY, USA,.
- Jimenez, A., Delgado, D., Merino, R., & Argumedo, A. (2022). A Decolonial Approach to Innovation? Building Paths Towards Buen Vivir. *The Journal of Development Studies*, 58(9), 1633–1650. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220388.2022.2043281>
- Karatasli, S. S., & Kumral, S. (2017). Great convergence or the third great divergence?: Changes in the global distribution of wealth, 1500–2008. In *The world-system as unit of analysis* (pp. 36–49). Routledge.
- Katz-Rosene, R. (2019). The Treatment of Global Environmental Change in the Study of International Political Economy: An Analysis of the Field's Most Influential Survey Texts. *International Studies Review*, 21(3), 477–496.
- Khasru, S. M., & Ambrizzi, T. (2023). Climate Change & Just Energy Transition: What the North Can Learn from the South? *CEBRI-Revista: Brazilian Journal of International Affairs*, 8, 166–193.
- King, R., Benton, T., Froggatt, A., Harwatt, H., Quiggin, D., & Wellesley, L. (2023). *The emerging global crisis of land use*. Chatham house. <https://www.chathamhouse.org/sites/default/files/2023-11/2023-11-22-emerging-global-crisis-land-use-king-et-al.pdf>
- Klingebliel, S. (2023). Geopolitics, the Global South and Development Policy. In *IDOS Policy Brief 14/2023* (Version 1.0). German Institute of Development and Sustainability. <https://doi.org/10.23661/IPB14.2023>
- Klingebliel, S., & Sumner, A. (2025). *Four futures for a global development cooperation system in flux: Policy at the intersection of geopolitics, norm contestation and institutional shift*. IDOS Policy Brief.
- Lahoti, R., Jayadev, A., & Reddy, S. (2016). The global consumption and income project (GCIP): An overview. *Journal of Globalization and Development*, 7(1), 61–108.
- Lauer, A., Carpintero, Ó., & De Castro, C. (2025). In search of a missing South: An explorative study of biases in global climate and energy scenarios. *Globalizations*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14747731.2025.2526295>
- Lauer, A., De Castro, C., & Carpintero, Ó. (2025). Beyond Green capitalism: Global scenarios for fast societal transitions toward sustainability. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 56, 100981. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2025.100981>
- Lauer, A., & Llases, L. (2025). *MORDRED: Model Of Resource Distribution and Resilient Economic Development. Model Documentation*. GitHub. <https://github.com/Pendracus/MORDRED>
- Matthews, H. D. (2016). Quantifying historical carbon and climate debts among nations. *Nature Climate Change*, 6(1), 60–64. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2774>
- Mazzega, P., Rugmini, D. M., & Barros-Platiau, A. F. (2025). Where is the “Global South” located in scientific research? *Earth System Governance*, 25, 100269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esg.2025.100269>
- Meadows, D. H., Meadows, D., Randers, J., & Behrens, W. W. (1972). *The limits to growth. A report for the Club of Rome's Project on the Predicament of Mankind*. Universe Books.

- Mohan, V. (2025). In search of consensus: Examining Global South perspectives on climate security in UNSC debates. *Earth System Governance*, 23, 100231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esg.2024.100231>
- Mohapatra, N. K. (2017). Energy security paradigm, structure of geopolitics and international relations theory: From global south perspectives. *GeoJournal*, 82(4), 683–700. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10708-016-9709-z>
- Moore, S. (2024). Climate Action in the Age of Great Power Rivalry: What Geopolitics Means for the Climate. *Kleinman Center for Energy Policy*.
- Muiderman, K., Vervoort, J., Gupta, A., Norbert-Munns, R. P., Veeger, M., Muzammil, M., & Driessen, P. (2023). Is anticipatory governance opening up or closing down future possibilities? Findings from diverse contexts in the Global South. *Global Environmental Change*, 81, 1–19.
- Nilsen, A. G. (2025). *Emerging Powers and the Political Economy of the Southern Interregnum*. 1–24.
- Ocholla, G. O., Bunyasi, M. M., Asoka, G. W., Pacha, O., Mbugua, H. K., Mbuthi, P., Mbiti, S., Wendo, H. K., & Kamau, P. K. (2013). Environmental issues and socio-economic problems emanating from salt mining in Kenya; a case study of Magarini district. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(3), 213–223.
- Our World in Data. (2024). *CO₂ emissions per capita*. https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/co-emissions-per-capita?country=OWID_AFR~OWID_SAM~OWID_EUR
- Owen, J. R., Kemp, D., Harris, J., Lechner, A. M., & Lèbre, É. (2022). Fast track to failure? Energy transition minerals and the future of consultation and consent. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 89, 102665.
- Owen, J. R., Kemp, D., Lechner, A. M., Harris, J., Zhang, R., & Lèbre, É. (2022). Energy transition minerals and their intersection with land-connected peoples. *Nature Sustainability*, 1–9.
- Parson, E. A., & Reynolds, J. L. (2021). Solar geoengineering: Scenarios of future governance challenges. *Futures*, 133, 102806.
- Ramirez, C. H. (2025). The Post-War Evolution of Globalisation and International Order: From Liberal to Neoliberal International Order. *Global Society*, 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600826.2025.2470838>
- Richardson, K., Steffen, W., Lucht, W., Bendtsen, J., Cornell, S. E., Donges, J. F., Drüke, M., Fetzer, I., Bala, G., & von Bloh, W. (2023). Earth beyond six of nine planetary boundaries. *Science Advances*, 9(37), eadh2458.
- Scheidel, A., Sorman, A. H., Avila, S., Del Bene, D., & Ott, J. (2023). Renewables Grabbing. Land and Resource Appropriations in the Global Energy Transition. In A. Neef, C. Ngin, T. Moreda, & S. Mollett (Eds.), *Routledge handbook of global land and resource grabbing* (pp. 189–204). Routledge.
- Sekera, J., & Lichtenberger, A. (2020). Assessing carbon capture: Public policy, science, and societal need: A review of the literature on industrial carbon removal. *Biophysical Economics and Sustainability*, 5, 1–28.
- Sène, A. L. (2024). Justice in nature conservation: Limits and possibilities under global capitalism. *Climate and Development*, 16(9), 838–847. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2023.2274901>
- Shan, Y. (2023). Discussion on How Climate Change is Disproportionately Affecting the Global South. *International Journal of Frontiers in Sociology*, 5(12). <https://doi.org/10.25236/IJFS.2023.051202>

- Surprise, K. (2020). Stratospheric imperialism: Liberalism,(eco) modernization, and ideologies of solar geoengineering research. *Environment and Planning E: Nature and Space*, 3(1), 141–163.
- Sus, M., & Hadeed, M. (2020). Theory-infused and policy-relevant: On the usefulness of scenario analysis for international relations. *Contemporary Security Policy*, 41(3), 432–455. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13523260.2020.1730055>
- Temper, L., Avila, S., Del Bene, D., Gobby, J., Kosoy, N., Le Billon, P., Martinez-Alier, J., Perkins, P., Roy, B., & Scheidel, A. (2020). Movements shaping climate futures: A systematic mapping of protests against fossil fuel and low-carbon energy projects. *Environmental Research Letters*, 15(12), 123004.
- Venier-Cambron, C., Helm, L. T., Malek, Ž., & Verburg, P. H. (2024). Representing justice in global land-use scenarios can align biodiversity benefits with protection from land grabbing. *One Earth*, 7(5), 896–907. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2024.03.006>
- Vuola, M. (2022). The intersections of mining and neoliberal conservation. *World Development*, 152, 105816. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2022.105816>
- Zondi, S. (2016). Ubuntu and sumak kawsay: The Inter-Parliamentary Union and the search for a global South humanist paradigm of development. *South African Journal of International Affairs*, 23(1), 107–120. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10220461.2016.1160838>